

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Abstract: as we carry out musical education and upbringing in the "musical culture" classes of secondary schools, the teacher first of all instills enthusiasm and interest in the art of music conveyed to students through knowledge, learned melodies and songs. will shoot. At school, especially in the elementary grades, interest and inclination to sing, listen to music is gradually formed, and the positive attitude and needs of young people to the art of music are formed.

Keywords: education, method, methodology, knowledge, skills and abilities, skill, art, attitude.

Introduction.

Music lessons are both artistic and educational in nature. Making it colorful, meaningful and interesting requires great pedagogical and professional skills from every teacher. "It is very difficult to teach art to students," says the well-known composer and pedagogue D. B. Kabalevsky, "the whole difficulty is that it is absolutely impossible to teach them real art without creating an emotional interest in them.

It is of particular importance to ensure the creative activity of students in these music lessons. Understanding music, enjoying its emotional impact depends on the participation of emotional experiences, as well as knowledge, skills and abilities. The more active and deep the feelings are in performing and perceiving the work, the more conscious and effective it is to understand and master them, to be influenced by them. These situations are a process that occurs as a result of creative activity. After all, a boring and monotonous lesson cannot create a lively emotional state. Students' interest in the lesson depends primarily on the chosen repertoire and methods (traditional or interactive) for listening and performance. The main criterion for choosing a repertoire of works for primary classes depends on their age, interest, knowledge and skill level. Accordingly, the methods used should be more playful. Works organized in the form of various selections on the theme of song, dance, fairy-tale characters, animals, birds, plants, natural landscapes are suitable for the children's world, they learn and develop their aesthetic feelings and musical abilities. The use of both modern and folk songs, works of sister nations and composers makes the lessons more meaningful and active, has a strong influence on the formation of love and affection for the heritage of folk music. enough young people. Creative activity is carried out in every lesson.

Lessons of modern music culture can be considered artistic and pedagogical work. Because the teacher creates it based on his personal creativity and experience. The composition and dramaturgy of the lesson, its artistic and pedagogical idea, goals and tasks, forms, methodological techniques and technologies are used to increase students' interest in music and educational materials, to instill in them the spiritual content of musical art and culture. is used, understanding modern musical creativity - all this is a product of the teacher's

creative approach. When planning a music lesson (one hour), the teacher determines the goal, task, topic, types and forms of teaching, musical activities and the knowledge, methods and technologies that should be conveyed to students in their content, and then prepares the lesson script. Each lesson of the lesson: listening to music, singing in a choir, musical literacy, rhythmic movements, performance on children's musical instruments should be connected and integrated. Various technologies, tools, techniques and techniques are used to actively involve students in the lesson. It is known that any pedagogical technology is based on educational principles that develop a new educational project and should be oriented to the student's personality. Cooperation between teacher and student, student and teacher should be organized based on modern requirements. In this process, the skills of working in cooperation with students are formed. In contrast to the methodological development of the educational process aimed at the active and effective activity of students, the pedagogical technology of teaching is focused on students, and also takes into account their individual and joint activities with the teacher, creating conditions for mastering the material. .

The choice of the type of pedagogical technology depends on the level of knowledge and skills to be mastered in lessons and training. Many technologies are used in the educational process. These technologies are designed for the age characteristics of students, mass education or individual education.

"Zig-zag" strategy method.

The method serves to work with students in a group, to master the subject quickly and deeply. The advantage of the method is determined by the following aspects:

- 1) students develop the ability to work in a team (or group);
- 2) time spent on mastering the subject is saved.

The process of applying the "Zig-zag" strategy includes the following actions:

Class students are divided into several (3-4 groups); the text explaining the essence of the new topic is divided into 3-4 parts, respectively; each group is given a certain part of the topic (text 1, text 2, etc.) and is assigned the task of studying it; in order to save time, among the members of the group, fast-reading students are selected who will sing; fast learners' ideas can be supplemented by groups; all groups read the text given to them (what musical genre is musical drama? Give examples of musical dramas created by Uzbek composers; tell about the art of conducting) after thoroughly mastering the texts, exchange texts between groups is increased; at this stage, the above activity is repeated; from this point of view, the students study the whole text which illuminates the essence of the topic.

Below are descriptions of some training (technologies) that can be used in the educational process: the "network" method is aimed at teaching the student to think logically, to expand the range of general ideas, to use literature independently. "3x4" methodology is focused on the students' ability to think freely, to present various ideas in a wide range, to analyze, to draw conclusions, to give definitions in the educational process individually and in small groups.

The "Blitz" game method is aimed at teaching the correct organization of the sequence of actions, logical thinking, the ability to choose the right thing from various ideas and information based on the topic being studied.

Thus, the interest in using new pedagogical technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day. Because pedagogical technologies and interactive methods allow young students to acquire deep knowledge and skills easily and comfortably.

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